

1 **TITLE PAGE**

2 Diminished kinesthetic and visual motor imagery ability in adults with chronic low back
3 pain.

4

5

6

7

8

9

10

11

12

13

14

15

16

17

18 **Diminished kinesthetic and visual motor imagery ability in adults with chronic low**
19 **back pain.**

20 Mental task and chronic low back pain

21 Author Names

22 Roy La Touche^{1-4*} PhD; Mónica Grande-Alonso^{1,2} MSc; Ferran Cuenca-Martínez^{1,2}

23 MSc; Luis González-Ferrero¹ MSc; Luis Suso-Martí^{1,2} MSc; Alba Paris-Alemaný¹⁻⁴

24 MD.

- 25 1. Departamento de Fisioterapia, Centro Superior de Estudios
26 Universitarios La Salle, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Spain.
- 27 2. Motion in Brains Research Group, Institute of Neuroscience and
28 Sciences of the Movement (INCIMOV), Centro Superior de Estudios
29 Universitarios La Salle, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Spain
- 30 3. Instituto de Neurociencia y Dolor Craneofacial (INDCRAN), Madrid,
31 Spain
- 32 4. Instituto de Investigación Sanitaria del Hospital Universitario La Paz
33 (IdiPAZ), Madrid, Spain

34 ***Corresponding author.** Address: Facultad de Ciencias de la Salud, Centro Superior
35 de Estudios Universitarios La Salle, Calle la Salle, nº 10, 28023 Madrid, Spain.

36 Telephone: (+34) 91 740 19 80 Fax: (+34) 91 357 17 30

37 E-Mail: roylatouche@yahoo.es

38 **Abstract for Original Research Articles.**

39 Background: Low back pain (LBP) is the most prevalent musculoskeletal problem
40 among adults. It has been observed that patients with chronic pain have maladaptive
41 neuroplastic changes and difficulty in imagination processes.

42 Objective: To assess the ability of patients with chronic LBP (CLBP) to generate
43 kinesthetic and visual motor images and the time they spent on this mental task
44 compared with asymptomatic participants.

45 Design: Prospective, A cross-sectional study.

46 Setting: Primary health care center in Madrid, Spain.

47 Participants: A total of 200 participants were classified into two groups: asymptomatic
48 participants (n = 100) and patients with CLBP (n = 100).

49 Methods: After consenting to participate, all the recruited participants received a
50 sociodemographic questionnaire, a set of self-report measures and completed the
51 Revised Movement Imagery Questionnaire (MIQ-R).

52 Main Outcomes Measurements: Visual and Kinesthetic Motor Imagery Ability using
53 the Revised Movement Imagery Questionnaire (MIQ-R). A mental chronometry using a
54 stopwatch and psychosocial variables using self-reported questionnaires.

55 Results: Our results indicated that patients with CLBP had difficulty generating
56 kinesthetic and visual motor images and also took a longer time to imagine them. A
57 regression analysis indicated that in the CLBP group, the predictor variable for fear of
58 activity and coping symptom self-efficacy was visual motor imagery (explaining 16.2%
59 of the variance); however, the predictor variable for LBP disability and pain

60 management self-efficacy was kinesthetic motor imagery (explaining 17.8% of the
61 variance).

62 Conclusions: It appears that patients with CLBP have greater difficulty generating
63 visual and kinesthetic motor images compared with asymptomatic participants, and they
64 also need more time to perform these mental tasks.

65 Level of evidence: II

66

67

68

69

70

71

72

73

74

75

76

77

78

79 **Introduction**

80 Low back pain (LBP) is the most prevalent musculoskeletal problem among adults.

81 Several studies show that the prevalence rate can vary from 18.6% to 57.4%. LBP is the
82 main cause of disability in our society, with a high rate of chronicity and work
83 absenteeism [1,2].

84 Some studies show that the process of chronicity in patients with LBP is determined by
85 psychological factors, which when associated with the exacerbation of pain, generate
86 maladaptive neuroplastic changes at medullary and supramedullary levels. These
87 changes could explain why current research shows that patients with LBP have a
88 disorder in processes of imagination [3].

89 Motor Imagery (MI) is defined as the cognitive ability to generate movements mentally
90 without performing them, and involves the participation of brain areas related to the
91 planning and execution of the movement [4–6]. In terms of the cortical regions involved
92 in the MI process, several studies related to cognition differ in their conclusions
93 regarding the role of the primary motor cortex. It is suggested that the posterior
94 cerebellum participates in MI implementing the inhibition of the execution of real
95 movement [7]. In addition, numerous studies have observed a significant influence of
96 the prefrontal cortex, motor supplementary area, premotor cortex (PC), anterior
97 cingulate cortex and posterior parietal cortex (PPC) in the process of imagining a motor
98 task [8-10]. The PPC is responsible for identifying the location of the body by
99 integrating information from the visual, auditory and somatosensory systems.

100 Moreover, during movement planning, the PPC and PC are responsible for decision
101 making, the anticipation of a movement and the specificity of the action as performed or
102 imagined [10].

103 Considering the subcortical regions, numerous studies suggest the possible participation
104 of basal ganglia and the cerebellum in the MI process [11]. Both are responsible for the
105 beginning of movement, generating an influence on basic cognitive processes and also
106 regulating the intensity of stereotyped movements [12].

107 Although scientific evidence is scarce, it has been observed that patients with chronic
108 LBP (CLBP) present an alteration in sensorimotor organization at the cortical level. One
109 study shows that patients with CLBP present significant differences in the participation
110 of the areas involved in the process of action observation compared with asymptomatic
111 participants [13]. That same research shows that movement planning in patients with
112 CLBP is dysfunctional, and that patients also present alterations in anticipatory postural
113 adjustments, which could be due to pain and associated psychological factors [13,14].

114 Neuroimaging studies have also found that patients with CLBP have differences
115 compared with asymptomatic participants at the neurobiochemical level. These changes
116 have been observed to be directly proportional to the process of chronification and to
117 psychological influences [15,16].

118 The main objective of this study was to evaluate the ability to generate both kinesthetic
119 and visual motor images, as well as to assess the time spent on this mental task by
120 patients with CLBP compared with asymptomatic participants. The secondary objective
121 was to analyze whether there were relationships between the ability to generate motor
122 imagery, the time employed and psychological and disability variables.

123 **Methods**

124 Study Design

125 A cross-sectional study design with a nonprobabilistic sample was used to assess visual
126 and kinesthetic movement imagery ability and psychosocial variables in patients with
127 CLBP compared with asymptomatic participants in a control group (CG). The trial was
128 conducted in accordance with the Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies
129 in Epidemiology (STROBE) statement [17].

130 Following the Helsinki Declaration, our study was approved by the Ethics Committee
131 for Clinical Research of a public reference hospital in Madrid (Spain), and written
132 informed consent was obtained from all the participants (PI-2567).

133 Participants

134 A consecutive non-probabilistic convenience sample of 100 patients with CLBP and
135 100 asymptomatic participants for the CG were recruited between January and July of
136 2017. The sample was recruited from outpatients of a primary health care center in
137 Madrid, Spain. The CG was recruited from our university campus and the local
138 community through flyers, posters and social media.

139 Inclusion criteria

140 Patients in the CLBP group were selected if they met all of the following inclusion
141 criteria: (a) low back pain in at least the prior 3 months; (b) low back pain of
142 nonspecific nature; and (c) men and women aged 18 to 65 years.

143 Asymptomatic participants were examined and included in the CG if they met the
144 following criteria: (a) had not had low back pain in the last 3 months; (b) men and
145 women aged 18 to 65 years.

146 Exclusion criteria

147 Patients in the CLBP group were excluded if they met one of the following exclusion
148 criteria: (a) neurological signs (such as weakness perceived in the lower limbs); (b)
149 specific spinal pathology (e.g., malignancy, inflammatory joint or bone diseases); (c)
150 having undergone back surgery.

151 The following general exclusion criteria are common to both groups: (a) any cognitive
152 disability that hinders visual and kinesthetic movement imagery ability; (b) illiteracy;
153 (c) understanding or communication difficulties; and (d) insufficient Spanish language
154 comprehension to follow study instructions.

155 Procedure

156 After consenting to participate, all the recruited participants received a
157 sociodemographic questionnaire to complete on the day of the assessment, which
158 recorded sex, date of birth, marital status and educational level. Next, each participant
159 completed a set of self-report measures. Finally, each participant completed the Revised
160 Movement Imagery Questionnaire (MIQ-R), evaluating, in addition, the time spent in
161 accomplishing the tasks of this questionnaire. The Spanish validated version of these
162 questionnaires was used, and this procedure was the same in both groups.

163 Primary Outcomes

164 Visual and Kinesthetic Motor Imagery Ability

165 MIQ-R is an 8-item self-report inventory and it was used to assess visual and
166 kinesthetic motor imagery ability. Four different movements are included in the MIQ-R
167 and the inventory is comprised of four visual and four kinesthetic items. For each item,
168 participants read a description of the movement. They then physically performed the

169 movement and were instructed to re-assume the starting position after finishing the
170 movement and before performing the mental task, which was to imagine the movement
171 visually or kinesthetically. A modification was made in the MIQ-R. Items 2 and 5, in
172 which a small jump is performed, were changed to standing on tiptoe. Next, each
173 participant rated the ease or difficulty of generating the mental image on a 7-point scale,
174 in which 7 indicated "very easy to see/feel" and 1 "very difficult to see/feel". The time
175 to perform each item was also evaluated. The internal consistencies of the MIQ-R have
176 been shown to be adequate, with Cronbach's α coefficients ranging above 0.84 for the
177 total scale, 0.80 for the visual subscale and 0.84 for the kinesthetic subscale [18].

178 Mental Chronometry

179 A mental chronometry evaluation was also used to measure the subject's motor imagery
180 ability. Using a stopwatch, the time spent performing each MIQ-R task was recorded.
181 The time recorded corresponded to the interval between the command to start the task,
182 given by the evaluator, and the verbal response that the task had been concluded, given
183 by the subject. Mental chronometry is a reliable behavioral task that has been previously
184 employed to obtain an objective measure of MI ability [19-21].

185 Secondary Outcomes

186 Low Back Disability

187 Physical disability due to LBP was assessed using the Spanish version of the Roland-
188 Morris Disability Questionnaire (RMDQ), which has been shown to have acceptable
189 psychometric properties. The RMDQ is a 24-item self-administered questionnaire, and
190 the total score ranges from 0 to 24, with the highest scores indicating the highest degree
191 of disability [22].

192 Pain-related fear

193 Pain-related fear of movement was assessed using the 11-item Spanish version of the
194 Tampa Scale of Kinesiophobia (TSK-11), whose reliability and validity have been
195 demonstrated [23]. The TSK-11 consists of two subscales, one related to fear of activity
196 and the other related to fear of harm. The final score can range between 11 and 44
197 points, with higher scores indicating greater perceived kinesiophobia.

198 Pain Catastrophizing

199 The Spanish version of the Pain Catastrophizing Scale (PCS) assesses the degree of
200 pain catastrophizing and is a reliable and valid measure of this phenomenon. It is
201 composed of 13 items and a 3-factor structure of rumination, magnification, and
202 helplessness, which must be answered with numeric values between 0 (not at all) and 4
203 (all the time), and with a maximum score of 52 points. Higher scores indicate greater
204 pain catastrophizing [24].

205 Self-efficacy

206 Self-efficacy was assessed through the Spanish version of the Chronic Pain Self-
207 Efficacy Scale (CPSS), which has been shown to have acceptable psychometric
208 properties [25]. The scale was developed to measure perceived self-efficacy and ability
209 to cope with the consequences of pain in patients with chronic pain. This scale is a 19-
210 item, self-administered instrument comprising three domains that assess self-efficacy
211 for pain management, physical functioning and coping with symptoms. Higher scores
212 indicate greater self-efficacy for managing pain.

213 Sample Size

214 The sample size was estimated with G*Power 3.1.7 for Windows (G*Power© from
215 University of Dusseldorf, Germany) [26]. This process was considered a power
216 calculation to detect between-group differences in the ability to generate motor imagery.
217 An independent sample Student's t-test analysis was used to detect the mean difference
218 between groups because it was the main factor of interest. The estimation was based on
219 a pilot study with a sample of 12 participants (six from the patient group and six from
220 the control group). A medium effect size of 0.55 was used to obtain 95% statistical
221 power ($1-\beta$ error probability) with an α error level probability of 0.05, suggesting a
222 sample size of 174 participants (87 per group).

223

224 The secondary objective of this study suggests the creation of a regression analysis to
225 assess the association between visual and kinesthetic movement imagery ability with
226 psychological and disability variables. It was thus necessary to enlarge the sample,
227 considering that we are using 10 predictors. In all, it was estimated that a total of 100
228 participants for each group of patients would be required (10 patients per predictor
229 variable). For the regression analysis, the rule of between 5 and 10 participants per
230 predictor variable was applied to obtain reasonably stable estimates of the regression
231 coefficients [27].

232 Analysis Data

233 The sociodemographic and clinical characteristics of the participants were analyzed.
234 The data were summarized using frequency counts, descriptive statistics, summary
235 tables and figures.

236 The data analysis was performed using the Statistics Package for Social Science (SPSS
237 20.00, IBM Inc., USA). The categorical variables are shown as frequencies and
238 percentages. The quantitative results of the study are represented by descriptive
239 statistics (confidence interval [CI], mean, and standard deviation [SD]). For all
240 variables, the z-score was assumed to follow a normal distribution based on the central
241 limit theorem because all the groups had more than 30 participants [28,29]. Student t-
242 test was used for the group comparisons. Cohen's *d* effect sizes were calculated for
243 multiple comparisons of the outcome variables. According to Cohen's method, the
244 magnitude of the effect was classified as small (0.20–0.49), medium (0.50–0.79) or
245 large (0.80).

246 The relationships between psychological measures, as well as the ability to generate
247 both kinesthetic and visual motor images was examined using Pearson correlation
248 coefficients. A Pearson correlation coefficient greater than 0.60 indicated a strong
249 correlation, a coefficient between 0.30 and 0.60 indicated a moderate correlation and a
250 coefficient below 0.30 indicated a low or very low correlation [30].

251

252 A multiple linear regression analysis was performed to estimate the strength of the
253 associations between the ability to generate both kinesthetic and visual motor images.
254 Psychological and disability variables were used as predictors. Variance inflation
255 factors (VIFs) were calculated to determine whether there were any multicollinearity
256 issues in any models. The strength of the association was examined using regression
257 coefficients (β), *p* values, and adjusted R^2 . Standardized beta coefficients were reported
258 for each predictor variable included in the final reduced models to allow for a direct
259 comparison between the predictor variables in the regression model and the criterion

260 variable being studied. For the data analysis, we used a CI of 95%, considering all those
261 values that had a p value of less than 0.05 to be statistically significant.

262 **Results**

263 The baseline sociodemographic characteristics of the sample are summarized in Table
264 1. The total study sample consisted of 200 participants (124 women and 76 men).

265 Table 1 shows that there were no statistically significant differences between groups in
266 relation to sociodemographic variables except for marital status. There were no
267 statistically significant differences for age, sex and education level between groups.

268 Visual and Kinesthetic Motor Imagery Ability

269 Patients with CLBP had difficulty in generating kinesthetic and visual motor images
270 and took longer to imagine them. The independent sample Student's t -test revealed
271 significant inter-group differences between both the kinesthetic ($F = 2.26, p < .01, d =$
272 0.76) and visual MIQ-R scores ($F = 11.44, p < .01, d = 0.57$) with a moderate effect
273 size. There were also significant inter-group differences in the time spent on the
274 imagination task, both kinesthetic ($F = 29.70, p < .01, d = -0.68$) and visual ($F = 7.15, p$
275 $< .01, d = -0.86$). There were also statistically significant differences in the scores for
276 the psychosocial variables. Table 2 shows the between-group comparisons.

277 Correlation Analysis

278 Table 3 shows the results of the correlation analysis, examining the bivariate
279 relationships among psychological measures, as well as the ability to generate both
280 kinesthetic and visual motor images and the time employed by the participants. The
281 strongest correlations were found in the analysis for the CLBP group, in which a

282 negative association was found between the ability to generate visual motor images and
283 a fear of activity ($r = -.371, p < .01$). In addition, there was a negative association with
284 the kinesthetic motor imagery ability ($r = -.291, p < .05$). A moderately positive
285 relationship was found between self-efficacy for the pain management subscale and the
286 ability to generate motor images, and a moderately negative association was found
287 between perceived disability and the ability to generate both visual and kinesthetic
288 motor images, with a stronger association in the kinesthetic subscale ($r = -.399, p < .01$).

289 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

290 The regression models for criterion variables (MIQ-R visual subscale and MIQ-R
291 kinesthetic subscale) are presented in Tables 4 and 5.

292 In the first model, as shown in Table 4, the criterion variable MIQ-R visual subscale
293 was predicted by the fear of activity subscale of the TSK-11, and by self-efficacy for
294 coping with symptoms as measured with the CPSS (for the CLBP group), thus
295 explaining 16.2% of the variance. The fear of harm subscale ($\beta = .097, p = .003$), total
296 TSK-11 ($\beta = .171, p = .519$), PCS rumination subscale ($\beta = -.023, p = .813$), PCS
297 magnification subscale ($\beta = .047, p = .630$), PCS helplessness subscale ($\beta = -.017, p =$
298 $.865$), total PCS scale ($\beta = -.018, p = .859$), RMDQ ($\beta = -.128, p = .255$), CPSS physical
299 functioning subscale ($\beta = .125, p = .297$) and CPSS pain management subscale ($\beta =$
300 $.036, p = .722$) were not significant predictors.

301 In the second model, as presented in Table 5, the criterion variable MIQ-R kinesthetic
302 subscale was predicted by disability as measured with RMDQ and by self-efficacy for
303 pain management as measured with the CPSS (for the CLBP group), thus explaining
304 17.8% of the variance. The fear of activity subscale ($\beta = -.136, p = .179$), fear of harm

305 subscale ($\beta = .000, p = 1.000$), total TSK-11 ($\beta = -.098, p = .348$), PCS rumination
306 subscale ($\beta = -.132, p = .218$), PCS magnification subscale ($\beta = -.075, p = .463$), PCS
307 helplessness subscale ($\beta = -.145, p = .192$), total PCS scale ($\beta = .136, p = .216$), CPSS
308 physical functioning subscale ($\beta = .000, p = .998$) and CPSS coping with symptoms
309 subscale ($\beta = .133, p = .217$) were not significant predictors.

310 **Discussion**

311 The main objective of this research was to analyze the ability to generate both
312 kinesthetic and visual motor images, in addition to the time used for these mental tasks,
313 in patients with CLBP compared with asymptomatic subjects. Based on the results, it
314 appears that patients with CLBP have greater difficulty in generating both visual and
315 kinesthetic motor images compared with asymptomatic subjects. They also use more
316 time to perform these mental tasks.

317 Ability to Generate Motor Images

318 We found that patients with CLBP had a lower ability to form kinesthetic motor images
319 and required a longer time to perform this task in comparison with asymptomatic
320 participants. These results are in agreement with current scientific evidence. Pijnenburg
321 et al [31] demonstrated that patients with CLBP needed more time to perform a mental
322 task. They also observed, through studies with neuroimaging, that there was a decrease
323 in functional connectivity between the various cortical areas involved in the process of
324 sensorimotor integration.

325 Additionally, Tagliazucchi et al [32] observed that the presence of maintained pain can
326 lead to an alteration at the cortical level, leading to increased activity of default mode
327 networks to the pain, even when the brain is in a state of rest. This process could lead to

328 an alteration in the functional connections related to motor planning and execution. In
329 patients with CLBP, information from the somatosensory complex might also be
330 corrupted by the presence of sustained pain. Therefore, patients with CLBP might
331 present with alterations in the input, integration and processing of the information, thus
332 affecting, by its similarity to the real motor activity, the ability to generate motor
333 images. These alterations are a possible explanation for the results obtained in the
334 present study. In a study performed using laterality training in asymptomatic
335 participants in various conditions, interference in the input was observed, generating
336 less successful results during the laterality test, thus concluding that if the information
337 input is defective the MI process could be altered [33].

338 Finally, it is important to note that numerous studies have affirmed that the presence of
339 chronic pain can generate a distortion of the affected area in the corporal representation
340 at the cortical level. This distortion could be another reason that patients with CLBP
341 present greater difficulty performing a mental task of a motor gesture, especially if that
342 gesture evokes the experience of pain. This distortion of the internal body representation
343 is due to a possible incongruence between the sensory inputs and the motor outputs
344 [34].

345 Influence of Psychological Factors on the Ability to Create Motor Images

346 Psychosocial variables play a critical role in the process of chronic pain ³. Patients with
347 a diagnosis of CLBP usually experience catastrophic thoughts about their pain as well
348 as fear avoidance behaviors in those motor gestures that have generated pain at some
349 time [35].

350 Based on the results obtained in this study, patients with CLBP presented statistically
351 significant differences in terms of the fear of movement variable with respect to

352 asymptomatic participants ($p < .001$), and also presented a negative correlation with
353 respect to the ability to generate both kinesthetic ($r = -.291, p < .05$) and visual motor
354 images ($r = -.371, p < .01$). In relation to these results, another study found that in
355 patients with regional complex pain syndrome, the action observation of various wrist
356 movements caused an increase in symptoms with significant differences compared to
357 the asymptomatic participants group [36]. In addition, it was found that the increased
358 pain when performing the action observation was positively correlated with a higher
359 score on the PCS scale and the TSK-11 scale [36]. This relationship could be explained
360 by the findings of another study that found, through neuroimaging, an attenuation of the
361 functional connection between the amygdala and the periaqueductal gray matter (which
362 is mainly responsible for endogenous analgesia) in patients with CLBP and high levels
363 of fear of movement [37]. Therefore, fear of movement could play a key role in the
364 presence of pain. Our hypothesis is that the input of painful somatosensory information
365 can affect the correct planning of movement, which could affect their subsequent ability
366 to imagine it.

367 The fear-avoidance model has also been analyzed regarding motor activity [38]. The
368 researchers observed that patients with high levels of fear presented alterations in
369 information processing. A possible cause for this finding is that these patients pay
370 excessive attention to potential signals of threat from the external environment, making
371 it more difficult to focus their attention on other tasks such as active movement.

372 Additionally, it was found that fear of movement is associated with the avoidance of
373 potentially painful movements. This avoidance underlies a syndrome of disuse and poor
374 motor performance [39]. It is possible that some of these phenomena also influence the
375 ability to generate motor images, another possible explanation for our results. That same

376 study also found positive correlations between the level of chronic pain self-efficacy
377 and the ability to generate kinesthetic motor images. A negative correlation was
378 observed between the perceived disability and the ability to generate kinesthetic motor
379 images. These data seem to suggest that presenting greater levels of self-efficacy, in the
380 presence of sustained pain along with a lower perception of disability, could have a
381 positive influence on the ability to generate kinesthetic motor images.

382 Some authors have assessed the self-efficacy variable and found an inverse relationship
383 between this variable and pain perception. Moreover, patients with higher levels of self-
384 efficacy showed less disability and obtained better results from their treatments [40,41].
385 It is therefore our hypothesis that the improvement of pain perception and a decrease in
386 disability that patients with greater levels of self-efficacy present could secondarily
387 improve their ability to generate kinesthetic motor images

388 Study Limitations

389 This study presents several limitations. The results obtained should be interpreted with
390 caution due to the fact that this is a cross-sectional study instead of a longitudinal study,
391 which precludes the ability to establish a cause-effect relationship.

392 The difficulty in generating motor images was studied through an instrument of self-
393 report and by a mental chronometry task. Although we consider these instruments to
394 have good reliability, it would be interesting for future studies to analyze the habit of
395 generating motor images using neural functional images. It would also be interesting to
396 measure the variability of the heart rate, because this measure seems to be more
397 sensitive for evaluating the association between autonomic nervous system activity and
398 the ability to perform motor imaging [42]. It is important to note that some authors

399 believe different measures are needed to identify the ability to generate motor images
400 [43].

401 Finally, we believe that it is a limitation to have performed no measures related to
402 movement or physical activity, to determine whether they could be associated with the
403 ability to generate motor images.

404 **Conclusions**

405 Based on our results, it appears that patients with CLBP have greater difficulty with
406 generating visual and kinesthetic motor images compared with asymptomatic
407 participants, and they also needed more time to perform the mental tasks.

408 Fear of movement and a greater perception of disability in patients with CLBP are
409 correlated with less ability to create kinesthetic motor images, and this ability is greater
410 in patients with higher levels of self-efficacy.

411 Further research is needed to improve our understanding and to be able to establish
412 clinical implications for the results obtained in this study.

413 **References**

- 414 1. Hoy D, Bain C, Williams G, et al. A systematic review of the global prevalence
415 of low back pain. *Arthritis Rheum* 2012;64(6):2028-2037. doi:10.1002/art.34347.
- 416 2. Rossignol M, Rozenberg S, Leclerc A. Epidemiology of low back pain: what's
417 new? *Joint Bone Spine* 2009;76(6):608-613. doi:10.1016/j.jbspin.2009.07.003.
- 418 3. Hashmi JA, Baliki MN, Huang L, et al. Shape shifting pain: Chronification of
419 back pain shifts brain representation from nociceptive to emotional circuits. *Brain*
420 2013;136(9):2751-2768. doi:10.1093/brain/awt211.
- 421 4. Frenkel MO, Herzig DS, Gebhard F, Mayer J, Becker C, Einsiedel T. Mental
422 Practice Maintains Range of Motion Despite Forearm Immobilization : a Pilot
423 Study in Healthy Persons. *J Rehabil Med* 2014;46(3):225-232.
424 doi:10.2340/16501977-1263.
- 425 5. Decety J. The neurophysiological basis of motor imagery. *Behav Brain Res*
426 1996;77(1-2):45-52.
- 427 6. Iseki K, Hanakawa T, Shinozaki J, Nankaku M, Fukuyama H. Neural
428 mechanisms involved in mental imagery and observation of gait. *Neuroimage*
429 2008;41(3):1021-1031. doi:10.1016/j.neuroimage.2008.03.010.
- 430 7. Lotze M, Montoya P, Erb M, et al. Activation of cortical and cerebellar motor
431 areas during executed and imagined hand movements: an fMRI study. *J Cogn*
432 *Neurosci* 1999;11(5):491-501.
- 433 8. Xu L, Zhang H, Hui M, et al. Motor execution and motor imagery : a comparison
434 of functional connectivity patterns based on graph theory. *Neuroscience*
435 2014;261(7):184-194. doi:10.1016/j.neuroscience.2013.12.005.

- 436 9. Guillot A, Collet C, Nguyen VA, Malouin F, Richards C, Doyon J. Brain
437 Activity During Visual Versus Kinesthetic Imagery : An fMRI Study. *Hum Brain*
438 *Mapp* 2009;30(7):2157-2172. doi:10.1002/hbm.20658.
- 439 10. Hanakawa T, Dimyan MA, Hallett M. Motor Planning , Imagery , and Execution
440 in the Distributed Motor Network : A Time- Course Study with Functional MRI.
441 *Cereb Cortex* 2008;18(12):2775-2788. doi:10.1093/cercor/bhn036.
- 442 11. Dominey P, Decety J, Broussolle E, Chazot G, Jeannerod M. Motor imagery of
443 lateralized sequential task is asymmetrically slowed in Hemi-Parkinson`s
444 patients. *Neuropsychologia* 1995;33(6):727-741.
- 445 12. Grush R. The emulation theory of representation: motor control, imagery, and
446 perception. *Behav Brain Sci* 2004;27(3):377-396.
- 447 13. Vrana A, Hotz-boendermaker S, Stämpfli P, et al. Differential Neural Processing
448 during Motor Imagery of Daily Activities in Chronic Low Back Pain Patients.
449 *PLoS One* 2015;10(11):1-18. doi:10.5061/dryad.2h0q3.
- 450 14. Bowering KJ, Connell NEO, Tabor A, et al. The Effects of Graded Motor
451 Imagery and Its Components on Chronic Pain: A Systematic Review and Meta-
452 Analysis. *J Pain* 2013;14(1):3-13. doi:10.1016/j.jpain.2012.09.007.
- 453 15. Grachev ID, Fredrickson BE, Apkarian A V. Brain chemistry reflects dual states
454 of pain and anxiety in chronic low back pain. *J Neural Transm*
455 2002;109(10):1309-1334. doi:10.1007/s00702-002-0722-7.
- 456 16. Lloyd D, Findlay G, Roberts N, Nurmikko T. Differences in Low Back Pain
457 Behavior Are Reflected in the Cerebral Response to Tactile Stimulation of the
458 Lower Back. *Spine* 2008;33(12):1372-1377.

- 459 17. Von Elm E, Altman DG, Egger M, et al. The Strengthening the Reporting of
460 Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) statement: guidelines for
461 reporting observational studies. *J Clin Epidemiol* 2008;61(4):344-349.
462 doi:10.1016/j.jclinepi.2007.11.008.
- 463 18. Campos A and González MA. Spanish version of the revised movement image
464 questionnaire (miq-r): psychometric properties and validation. *Rev Psicol del*
465 *Deport* 2010;19:263-273.
- 466 19. Guillot A, Collet C. Duration of Mentally Simulated Movement: A Review. *J*
467 *Mot Behav* 2005;37(1):10-20. doi:10.3200/JMBR.37.1.10-20.
- 468 20. Malouin F, Richards CL, Durand A, Doyon J. Reliability of Mental Chronometry
469 for Assessing Motor Imagery Ability After Stroke. *Arch Phys Med Rehabil*
470 2008;89(2):311-319. doi:10.1016/j.apmr.2007.11.006.
- 471 21. Williams SE, Guillot A, Di Rienzo F, Cumming J. Comparing self-report and
472 mental chronometry measures of motor imagery ability. *Eur J Sport Sci*
473 2015;15(8):703-711. doi:10.1080/17461391.2015.1051133.
- 474 22. Kovacs FM, Llobera J, Gil Del Real MT, et al. Validation of the spanish version
475 of the Roland-Morris questionnaire. *Spine* 2002;27(5):538-542.
- 476 23. Gómez-Pérez L, López-Martínez AE, Ruiz-Párraga GT. Psychometric Properties
477 of the Spanish Version of the Tampa Scale for Kinesiophobia (TSK). *J Pain*
478 2011;12(4):425-435. doi:10.1016/j.jpain.2010.08.004.
- 479 24. García Campayo J, Rodero B, Alda M, Sobradie N, Montero J, Moreno S.
480 Validation of the Spanish version of the Pain Catastrophizing Scale in
481 fibromyalgia. *Med Clin (Barc)* 2008;131(13):487-492.

- 482 25. Martín-Aragón M, Pastor Mira MA, Rodríguez Marím J, March MJ, Lledó A,
483 López-Roig S et al. Percepción de autoeficacia en dolor crónico. Adaptación y
484 validación de la Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy Scale. Rev Psicol Salud 1999;11(1-
485 2):53-75.
- 486 26. Faul F, Erdfelder E, Lang AG, Buchner A. G*Power 3: a flexible statistical
487 power analysis program for the social, behavioral, and biomedical sciences.
488 Behav Res Methods 2007;39(2):175-191.
- 489 27. Hair JF, Anderson RE, Tatham RL, Black WC. Multivariate Data Analysis
490 International Journal of Pharmaceutics 1998;131:816.
491 doi:10.1016/j.ijpharm.2011.02.019.
- 492 28. Mouri H. Log-normal distribution from a process that is not multiplicative but is
493 additive. Phys Rev E Stat Nonlin Soft Matter Phys 2013;88:042124.
494 doi:10.1103/PhysRevE.88.042124.
- 495 29. Nixon RM, Wonderling D, Grieve RD. Non-parametric methods for cost-
496 effectiveness analysis: the central limit theorem and the bootstrap compared.
497 Health Econ 2010;19(3):316-333. doi:10.1002/hec.1477.
- 498 30. Hinkle DE, Wiersma W, Jurs SG. Applied Statistics for the Behavioral Sciences.
499 Source J Educ Stat 1990;15(1):84-87.
- 500 31. Pijnenburg M, Brumagne S, Caeyenberghs K, et al. Resting-State Functional
501 Connectivity of the Sensorimotor and the Association with the Sit-to-Stand-to-Sit
502 Task. Brain Connect 2015;5(5):303-311. doi:10.1089/brain.2014.0309.
- 503 32. Tagliazucchi E, Balenzuela P, Fraiman D, Chialvo D. Brain resting state is
504 disrupted in chronic back pain patients. Neurosci Lett 2010;485(1):26-31.

- 505 doi:10.1016/j.neulet.2010.08.053.Brain.
- 506 33. McCormick K, Zalucki N, Hudson ML, Moseley GL. Faulty proprioceptive
507 information disrupts motor imagery : an experimental study. *Aust J Physiother*
508 2007;53(1):41-45. doi:10.1016/S0004-9514(07)70060-0.
- 509 34. Moseley GL, McCormick K, Hudson M, Zalucki N. Disrupted cortical
510 proprioceptive representation evokes symptoms of peculiarity , foreignness and
511 swelling , but not pain. *Rheumatology* 2006;45:196-200.
512 doi:10.1093/rheumatology/kei119.
- 513 35. Moseley GL. Evidence for a direct relationship between cognitive and physical
514 change during an education intervention in people with chronic low back pain.
515 *Eur J Pain* 2004;8(1):39-45. doi:10.1016/S1090-3801(03)00063-6.
- 516 36. Moseley GL, Zalucki N, Birklein F, et al. Thinking About Movement Hurts : The
517 Effect of Motor Imagery on Pain and Swelling in People With Chronic Arm Pain.
518 *Arthritis Rheum* 2008;59(5):623-631. doi:10.1002/art.23580.
- 519 37. Meier ML, Stämpfli P, Humphreys BK, Vrana A, Seifritz E, Schweinhardt P.
520 The impact of pain-related fear on neural pathways of pain modulation in chronic
521 low back pain. *PAIN Reports* 2017;2(3):e601.
522 doi:10.1097/PR9.0000000000000601.
- 523 38. Vlaeyen JW, Linton SJ. Fear-avoidance and its consequences in chronic
524 musculoskeletal pain: a state of the art. *Pain* 2000;85(3):317-332.
- 525 39. Crombez G, Vervaeke L, Lysens R, Baeyens F, Eelen P. Avoidance and
526 Confrontation of Painful, Back-Straining Movements in Chronic Back Pain
527 Patients. *Behav Modif* 1998;22(1):62-77. doi:10.1177/01454455980221004.

- 528 40. Strong J, Westbury K, Smith G, McKenzie I, Ryan W. Treatment outcome in
529 individuals with chronic pain: is the Pain Stages of Change Questionnaire
530 (PSOCQ) a useful tool? *Pain* 2002;97(1-2):65-73.
- 531 41. Turk DC, Okifuji A. Psychological factors in chronic pain: evolution and
532 revolution. *J Consult Clin Psychol* 2002;70(3):678-690.
- 533 42. Peixoto Pinto T, Mello Russo Ramos M, Lemos T, Domingues Vargas C,
534 Imbiriba LA. Is heart rate variability affected by distinct motor imagery
535 strategies? *Physiol Behav* 2017;177:189-195.
536 doi:10.1016/j.physbeh.2017.05.004.
- 537 43. Braun N, Kranczioch C, Liepert J, et al. Motor Imagery Impairment in Postacute
538 Stroke Patients. *Neural Plast* 2017;2017:1-13. doi:10.1155/2017/4653256.
- 539
- 540
- 541
- 542
- 543
- 544
- 545
- 546
- 547
- 548

549 **TABLES**

550 Table 1. Descriptive statistics for demographic variables (n = 200).

Measures	CG (n = 100)	CLBP (n = 100)	p value Independent Samples Student T- test or Chi-square tests
Age	38.82 ± 13.30	40.44 ± 13.71	.397*
Gender			.155†
Male	42 (42.0)	34(34.0)	
Female	58 (58.0)	66(66.0)	
Educational Level			.062†
Primary education	24 (24.0)	18 (18.0)	
Secondary education	29 (29.0)	18 (18.0)	
College education	47 (47.0)	64 (64.0)	
Marital Status			.002†
Single	36 (36.0)	24 (24.0)	
Married	57 (57.0)	56 (56.0)	
Stable couple	0 (0.0)	14 (14.0)	
Divorced	7 (7.0)	6 (6.0)	
Widow	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	

551 Values are presented as mean ± standard deviation or number (%). *: Independent Samples T-Student; †: Chi-square

552 tests; CG: Control group; CLBP: Chronic Low Back Pain.

553

554 Table 2. Between group comparisons.

Measures	CG	CLBP	Mean Differences (95%CI); Effect Size (<i>d</i>)
	(n = 100)	(n = 100)	
	M ± SD	M ± SD	
RMDQ	-	6.16 ± 4.58	-
TSK-11			
Total TSK-11	20.53 ± 5.46	26.39 ± 6.50	-5.85 (-7.51 to -4.18)** <i>d</i> = -0.97
TSK-FA	13.16 ± 3.62	16.97 ± 4.26	-3.81 (-4.90 to -2.71)** <i>d</i> = -0.96
TSK-FH	7.39 ± 2.46	9.39 ± 2.94	-2.00 (-2.75 to -1.24)** <i>d</i> = -0.73
PCS			
Total PCS	8.01 ± 8.29	14.79 ± 10.79	-6.78 (-9.43 to -4.12)** <i>d</i> = -0.70
PCS-R	3.19 ± 3.55	5.64 ± 4.23	-2.45 (-3.54 to -1.37)** <i>d</i> = -0.62
PCS-M	1.88 ± 2.09	3.32 ± 2.65	-1.43 (-2.09 to -0.77)** <i>d</i> = -0.60
PCS-H	3.00 ± 3.44	6.30 ± 5.11	-3.29 (-4.50 to -2.08)** <i>d</i> = -0.75
CPSS			
Total CPSS	164.47 ± 20.37	143.04 ± 30.07	21.42 (14.26 to 28.58)** <i>d</i> = 0.83
CPSS-CS	57.45 ± 4.59	52.04 ± 9.33	5.40 (3.33 to 7.47)** <i>d</i> = 0.73
CPSS-PF	66.90 ± 10.98	57.97 ± 13.76	8.93 (5.44 to 12.42)** <i>d</i> = 0.71
CPSS-PM	40.12 ± 8.60	33.21 ± 12.90	6.90 (3.84 to 9.96)** <i>d</i> = 0.63

MIQ-R			
MIQR-V	24.40 ± 2.86	22.48 ± 3.75	1.92 (0.99 to 2.84)** <i>d</i> = 0.57
MIQR-K	22.25 ± 4.51	18.53 ± 5.24	3.72 (2.36 to 5.08)** <i>d</i> = 0.76
MIQR-VT	18.29 ± 13.70	30.01 ± 20.16	-11.71 (-16.50 to -6.92)** <i>d</i> = -0.68
MIQR-KT	18.23 ± 13.30	35.70 ± 25.34	-17.46 (-23.10 to -11.82)** <i>d</i> = -0.86

555

556 ***p* < .01; M: Mean; SD: Standard Deviation; CG: Control Group; CLBP: Chronic Low Back Pain; RMDQ: Roland
557 Morris Disability Questionnaire; TSK-11: Tampa Scale for Kinesiophobia; TSK-FA: Fear of the activity subscale;
558 TSK-FH: Fear of the harm subscale; PCS: Pain Catastrophizing Scale; PCS-R: Rumination subscale, PCS-M:
559 Magnification subscale; PCS-H: Helplessness subscale; CPSS: Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy Scale; CPSS-CS: Coping
560 with symptoms subscale; CPSS-PF: Physical Functioning subscale; CPSS-PM: Pain management subscale; MIQ-R:
561 Revised Movement Imagery Questionnaire; MIQR-V: Visual subscale; MIQR-K: Kinesthetic subscale; MIQR-VT:
562 Time employed in Visual subscale; MIQR-KT: Time employed in Kinesthetic subscale.

563

564
565
566
567
568
569
570
571
572
573
574
575
576
577
578
579
580
581
582
583
584

Table 3. Pearson correlation coefficient between variables analyzed in the study in CLBP Group.

Measures	MIQR-V	MIQR-K	MIQR-VT	MIQR-KT
RMDQ	-.319**	-.399**	-.060	-.029
TSK-11				
TSK-FA	-.371**	-.291**	-.062	-.010
TSK-FH	-.224*	-.121*	-.032	-.029
PCS				
PCS-R	-.141	-.085	-.065	-.132
PCS-M	-.085	-.093	-.041	-.032
PCS-H	-.165	-.113	-.057	-.075
CPSS				
CPSS-CS	.315**	.324**	.009	-.030
CPSS-PF	.303**	.274**	.109	.089
CPSS-PM	.313**	.373**	-.053	-.107

585 * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; CLBP: Chronic Low Back Pain; RMDQ: Roland Morris Disability Questionnaire; TSK-11: Tampa
586 Scale for Kinesiophobia; TSK-FA: Fear of the activity subscale; TSK-FH: Fear of the harm subscale; PCS: Pain
587 Catastrophizing Scale; PCS-R: Rumination subscale, PCS-M: Magnification subscale; PCS-H: Helplessness subscale;
588 CPSS: Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy Scale; CPSS-CS: Coping with symptoms subscale; CPSS-PF: Physical Functioning
589 subscale; CPSS-PM: Pain management subscale; MIQR-R: Revised Movement Imagery Questionnaire; MIQR-V:
590 Visual subscale; MIQR-K: Kinesthetic subscale; MIQR-VT: Time employed in Visual subscale; MIQR-KT: Time
591 employed in Kinesthetic subscale.

592

593

594

595

596

597

Table 4. Multiple linear regression analysis for MIQ-R Visual Subscale in CLBP group

Group	Regression	Standardized	<i>p</i> -value	VIF	Overall model		
	coefficient	coefficient			<i>R</i> ²	Adjusted	<i>F</i>
	(<i>B</i>)	(<i>β</i>)			<i>R</i> ²		
CLBP					.179	.162	10.36
Predictor variable							
TSK-FA	-.257	-.295	.003	1.091			
CPSS-CS	.092	.23	.02	1.091			
Excluded variable							
Total TSK-11		.171	.519	8.079			
TSK-FH		.097	.414	1.608			
Total PCS		-.018	.859	1.118			
PCS-R		-.023	.813	1.078			
PCS-M		.047	.630	1.077			
PCS-H		-.017	.865	1.171			
RMDQ		-.128	.255	1.443			
CPSS-PF		.125	.297	1.639			
CPSS-PM		.036	.722	1.138			

599

600 VIF, variance inflation factor; CLBP: Chronic Low Back Pain; RMDQ: Roland Morris Disability Questionnaire; TSK-
 601 11: Tampa Scale for Kinesiophobia; TSK-FA: Fear of the activity subscale; TSK-FH: Fear of the harm subscale; PCS:
 602 Pain Catastrophizing Scale; PCS-R: Rumination subscale, PCS-M: Magnification subscale; PCS-H: Helplessness
 603 subscale; CPSS: Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy Scale; CPSS-CS: Coping with symptoms subscale; CPSS-PF: Physical
 604 Functioning subscale; CPSS-PM: Pain management subscale; MIQ-R: Revised Movement Imagery Questionnaire;
 605 MIQR-V: Visual subscale; MIQR-K: Kinesthetic subscale; MIQR-VT: Time employed in Visual subscale; MIQR-
 606 KT: Time employed in Kinesthetic subscale.

607

608

609 Table 5. Multiple linear regression analysis for MIQ-R Kinesthetic Subscale in CLBP group

Group	Regression	Standardized	<i>p</i> -value	VIF	Overall model		
	coefficient	coefficient			<i>R</i> ²	Adjusted	<i>F</i>
	(<i>B</i>)	(β)			<i>R</i> ²		
CLBP					.195	.178	11.47
Predictor variable							
RMDQ	-.370	-.330	.001	1.134			
CPSS-PM	.081	.200	.044	1.134			
Excluded variable							
Total TSK-11		-.098	.348	1.265			
TSK-FA		-.136	.179	1.201			
TSK-FH		.000	1.000	1.192			
Total PCS		.136	.216	1.420			
PCS-R		.132	.218	1.351			
PCS-M		-.075	.463	1.203			
PCS-H		-.145	.192	1.453			
CPSS-PF		.000	.998	1.649			
CPSS-CS		.133	.217	1.357			

611 VIF, variance inflation factor; CLBP: Chronic Low Back Pain; RMDQ: Roland Morris Disability Questionnaire; TSK-
 612 11: Tampa Scale for Kinesiophobia; TSK-FA: Fear of the activity subscale; TSK-FH: Fear of the harm subscale; PCS:
 613 Pain Catastrophizing Scale; PCS-R: Rumination subscale, PCS-M: Magnification subscale; PCS-H: Helplessness
 614 subscale; CPSS: Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy Scale; CPSS-CS: Coping with symptoms subscale; CPSS-PF: Physical
 615 Functioning subscale; CPSS-PM: Pain management subscale; MIQ-R: Revised Movement Imagery Questionnaire;
 616 MIQR-V: Visual subscale; MIQR-K: Kinesthetic subscale; MIQR-VT: Time employed in Visual subscale; MIQR-
 617 KT: Time employed in Kinesthetic subscale.

618